

Molybdenum Trioxide Surface Functionalized with Ruthenium(II) and Chitosan: Bio-functional Nanosystem

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Abstract

Environment-friendly approach for large-scale preparation of biomolecule functionalized metal oxide nanostructures are beneficial for fundamental and advanced health care applications [1,2]. Herein, molybdenum trioxide nanoparticles (MoO₃ NPs) are synthesized using asafoetida resin (natural product) as reducing agent and sequentially surface modified with ruthenium(II) [Ru(II)] and biomolecule, chitosan at room temperature. MoO₃ NPs were electrostatically modified with ruthenium(II) resulting into an optically active nanodispersion, exhibiting UV-vis absorbance at 216, 290 and 486 nm, respectively. Spectroscopic investigations revealed that the functional group of Mo-O-Mo⁺ and Mo=O⁻ mediated a cationic- π and anionic- π interactions with bipyridine ligands of Ru(II). Intermolecular interaction with the amine groups of chitosan have established a coordination bonding in MoO₃-Ru(II). It is expected that the chitosan layer modified on the surface of MoO₃-Ru(II) may promote biocompatibility suitable for bio-imaging and biosensor platform.

References

1. M. Veerapandian, P.K. Avti, V. Ravichandiran, Colloid. Surface B. 154(2017) 315–320.
2. M. Veerapandian, X.X. Zhu, S. Giasson, J. Mater. B 3(2015) 665-672.